

FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES WITH EMBEDDED OPTICAL FIBER SENSORS

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ABSTRACT

To investigate the effect of embedded optical fiber sensors on the mechanical properties of smart composite structures, the fatigue life of composite laminates with embedded optical fiber sensors was examined. Additionally, matrix cracking behavior of composite laminates with embedded optical fiber sensors under the fatigue loading and the fatigue life of embedded optical fiber sensor itself were also evaluated. All of testing specimens were fabricated with transparent glass fiber/epoxy composites in order to observe initiation and growth of damage in the specimens and laser signal behavior transmitted through the optical fiber visually and directly. From the various experiments, the embedded optical fibers were found to have significant effects on the fatigue life of composite laminates. However, the embedded optical fiber sensors did not show significant effect on the matrix cracking behavior under the fatigue loading. Finally, it was found that the fatigue resistance of embedded optical fiber sensors are very low and the observed fatigue limit of these sensors are around 15% of strength of host composite laminates.

INTRODUCTION

The use of optical fiber sensors in advanced polymer-based composites has been received much attention as part of research field of smart structure which would incorporate of sensing, actuating and signal processing, as well as the inherent mechanical functions associated with the material itself. Embedded or attached optical fiber sensors have been developed to determine structural behavior and to detect the onset of material degradation and damage during usage. Optical fiber sensors has a number of specific advantages over other types of sensors for application to smart structure. Optical fibers are small, lightweight and flexible. They can be easily embedded into host material such as composite laminates. They are immune to electromagnetic interference due to their dielectric nature and can measure many physical quantities simultaneously at many points. Additionally, optical fibers are highly resistant to environmental conditions and relatively inexpensive [1-3].

Although fiber optic sensors are quite small enough to be embedded easily in composite materials, their diameters are quite large in comparison with typical reinforcing fiber diameters or the thickness of a single layer of a composite laminates. For example, the typical optical fiber diameter is about 125 μm when their coating is removed, while the diameter of glass fiber is approximately 16 μm and a single layer of glass/epoxy laminates is approximately 100~300 μm

thick. The embedding of such an optical fiber can introduce geometric discontinuities and may cause reduction of the mechanical properties of host materials [4]. Thus, comprehensive investigations of the effects of embedded optical fibers on the mechanical behaviors of composite laminates became necessary. Several previous studies[5-7] were carried out concerning the behavior of composites with embedded optical fibers under static loads such as tension or compression. Their studies showed that the embedded optical fibers do not cause significant effect on the mechanical properties of host composite materials. However, since most real structures in service are subjected to variable and cyclic loads, the study on the effects of embedded optical fibers on the fatigue behaviors of composite laminates is required.

In the present study, we investigated the fatigue behavior of glass fiber/epoxy composites with embedded optical fibers for long-term characterization. All specimens used in this study were fabricated from transparent glass fiber/epoxy composites so that we can observe the damage initiation and propagation such as matrix cracking and bleeding of laser signal visually and directly. First, fatigue life data for unidirectional and crossply specimens with several different numbers of embedded optical fibers were obtained and compared to investigate the effects of the orientation and the quantity of embedded optical fibers on the fatigue life of glass/epoxy laminates. In the crossply specimens, resin rich area is formed around the optical fiber because the optical fiber embedded between transverse plies is perpendicular to adjacent reinforcing fibers. This resin rich area may cause the stress and strain concentration so that it may initiate the matrix crack which is major damage mode of transverse ply [4,8]. Thus, the effects of the stress and strain concentration on the development of matrix crack density under the cyclic loadswere also investigated by measuring and comparing matrix crack densities of crossply specimens with different numbers of embedded optical fiber sensors.

Additionally, in the application of smart structures, the integrity of embedded optical fiber sensor itself is also important problem to be carefully considered in addition to the fatigue life of host composite structures in which they are embedded. Thus, we also investigated the fatigue life of optical fiber itself embedded in the composite laminate from the separated tests and obtained S-N curve of embedded optical fiber.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTALS

All specimens were fabricated from SUNKYUNG INDUSTRY Co. UGN-150 glass fiber/epoxy prepregs. Two types of stacking sequence, which were unidirectional and crossply, were chosen to investigate the effect of the optical fiber embedded parallel and perpendicular to adjacent reinforcing fibers on the fatigue behaviors of laminates. All specimens were 200mm long and 24mm wide and had 38mm long E-glass loading tabs bonded to each end of specimens with CYANAMID FM 73 film adhesive, leaving a 124mm test section, as shown in Fig. 1. The specimens cured in a programmable autoclave with the manufacturer's recommended cure cycle to ensure uniform mechanical properties for each laminate.

SAMSUNG ELECTRONICS Co. single mode DSF(dispersion shifted fiber, DS-2 YAYH) were embedded in the neutral plane of laminates parallel to the loading direction. They are 250 μ m diameter of acrylate coated optical fibers which consist of 9 μ m core and 125 μ m cladding. The test section part of the acrylate coating of embedded optical fibers was removed to increase the sensitivity to damage as shown in Fig. 2.

To explore the effect of quantity of embedded optical fibers, five different numbers (0, 1, 3, 5 and 7) of optical fibers were embedded in the crossply specimens and two different numbers (0 and 3) of optical fibers were embedded in the unidirectional specimens so that seven specimen configurations could be obtained. The spacing between the optical fibers in a specimen were equal. Table 1 describes the specimen configurations with the stacking sequence, the number of

Figure 1. The geometry of a test specimen(all dimensions are mm).

Figure 2. Removal of coating when embedding an optical fiber in composite laminates.

embedded optical fibers and the number of test specimens. In this table, F, U and C in the specimen configuration mean fatigue, unidirectional and crossply specimen respectively. And the number in the specimen configuration means the number of embedded optical fibers. Additionally, to observe the fatigue life of embedded sensors, only one optical fiber was embedded in the unidirectional and crossply specimen.

Table 1. Details of specimen configurations.

Specimen configuration	Stacking type	Number of optical fibers	Number of test specimens
FU0	Unidirectional	0	5
FU3	Unidirectional	3	5
FC0	Crossply	0	5
FC1	Crossply	1	5
FC3	Crossply	3	5
FC5	Crossply	5	5
FC7	Crossply	7	5

The fatigue tests of composite laminates with embedded optical fibers were carried out under load control with a tensile sinusoidal waveform at a frequency of 4 Hz using MTS servo-hydraulic test machine. For crossply specimens whose stacking sequence is $[0/90_4]_S$, the maximum cyclic stress of 114MPa was selected to give higher stress than the stress of static transverse cracking threshold (about 100MPa) and the stress ratio, R , was 0. On the other hand, for unidirectional specimens whose stacking sequence is $[0_{10}]$, the maximum cyclic stress was chosen to 700MPa to give higher stress than the fatigue limit and stress ratio, R , was 0.1. The fatigue tests for the fatigue life of sensor with the specimens with embedded one optical fiber were carried out under load control with a tensile sinusoidal waveform at a frequency of 5Hz using MTS servo-hydraulic test machine. The maximum stresses in the range of 15~30% of strength of composite laminate shown in Table 2 were loaded and the stress ratio, R , was 0.1.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

FATIGUE LIFE

The fatigue life of both crossply and unidirectional specimens were determined from the cycle at the final fracture of the specimens. Fig. 3 and 4 show the fatigue life and average life for each configuration of crossply and unidirectional specimens, respectively. From these figures, it is observed that the embedded optical fiber reduces significantly the fatigue life of the composite laminate and the fatigue life of specimen embedded with increased number of optical fibers is reduced significantly. From this result, it can be said that embedded optical fibers have significant effect on the fatigue behavior of composite structure.

However, in these tests, the applied fatigue loads were about seventy percentage of laminate strength for both stacking sequences (the strength of the unidirectional specimen is 1004MPa and the crossply specimen is 160MPa). If we consider safety factor of structure design from an engineering view point, the applied fatigue load seems too high. Because of such a high fatigue load, fracture of the embedded optical fiber sensors occurs at the very early stage of fatigue life, that is, within a few dozen cycles for crossply specimen and during just first cycle for unidirectional specimen. This means that the fatigue life of both composite laminates and embedded optical fiber sensors cannot be evaluated simultaneously at the same load due to the much differences of stress and strain of fracture. So, we carried out another experiments concerning the fatigue life of embedded optical fiber. This topic will be described in the later section. The basic purpose of these fatigue tests was the evaluation of the fatigue life of

Figure 3. The fatigue lives for each configuration of crossply specimens under load control with a tensile sinusoidal waveform of 0~114MPa at a frequency of 4 Hz and stress ratio, R , of 0.

Figure 4. The fatigue lives for each configuration of unidirectional specimens under load control with a tensile sinusoidal waveform of 0~700MPa at a frequency of 4 Hz and stress ratio, R, of 0.1.

composite laminate with embedded optical fiber. For example, in unidirectional test case with 600MPa applied load, we stopped fatigue testing at 1.296×10^7 cycle without failure with over four days time consuming. To avoid fatigue limit and too much time consuming, high fatigue load was applied in these tests.

MATRIX CRACKING BEHAVIOR

For crossply specimens, 40mm of gage length is marked on the specimens and photographs of specimen were taken at designed cycle during the testing process to monitor the initiation and development of matrix cracks in the transverse ply. The values of load and strain were recorded together at that time. Then, the average values of matrix crack density at each cycle for each configuration were calculated and plotted in Fig. 5. Although the fatigue life of composite laminates were affected significantly by the embedded optical fibers, the matrix crack density didn't show such a significant effect as shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5. The average values of matrix crack density at the designed cycle for crossply specimens with four different numbers of embedded optical fiber.

LASER SIGNAL BEHAVIOR

The laser light from MELLES GRIOT 10mW He-Ne laser with $0.6328\mu\text{m}$ wavelength was introduced into the optical fiber embedded using a coupler, a lens and an optical fiber positioning assembly. The intensity of laser signal transmitted through the embedded optical fiber was measured using a SHARP BS142 photodiode to monitor the damage of embedded optical fiber sensors and associated laser signal behavior. The laser intensity signal transmitted through the optical fiber embedded in both unidirectional and crossply specimens was monitored during the tests. Data of cycle and laser intensity were recorded automatically using PC-based data acquisition system.

Fig. 6 represents typical graph of laser intensity changes transmitted through the optical fiber embedded in a crossply specimen with cycles of fatigue loading. As shown in this figure, the laser intensity fall off in a few dozen cycles after the occurrence of matrix crack. This means that the embedded optical fiber are very sensitive and have a low resistance to fatigue load. For example, in unidirectional specimens the fatigue life of embedded optical fiber was about 5×10^3 cycles at applied load 300MPa, which is well below of fatigue limit. The integrity of embedded optical fiber sensors in the smart structure working under cyclic load seems important problem to be considered carefully, in addition to significant reduction of fatigue life of composite laminates. In case of unidirectional specimen, since the maximum stress level of cyclic load was so high as to give the cyclic stress above the fatigue limit, the optical fiber was fractured during the initial loading of fatigue cycle. Therefore, as mentioned in the previous section, the fatigue behavior of embedded optical fibers should be treated with lower stress and will be described in the next section.

FATIGUE LIFE OF THE EMBEDDED OPTICAL FIBER

As mentioned earlier, it was noticed that the embedded optical fibers have a low resistance to fatigue loads, that is, the fatigue limit of embedded optical fiber sensors is well below the fatigue limit of composite laminates in which they are embedded. Because the integrity of embedded optical fiber sensors in the smart structure in service can be also another problem to be considered. Additional and separated fatigue tests were carried out under several cyclic stress levels and obtained the S-N curve for the embedded optical fiber itself. In the present experiment, a limited number of specimens of unidirectional specimens, $[0_{12}]_s$, and crossply specimens, $[0_2/90_4]_s$, were tested to obtain rough estimation of S-N trend. Further extensive

Figure 6. A typical graph of laser intensity changes transmitted through the optical fiber embedded in a crossply specimen and matrix crack density changes with cycles of fatigue loads.

Table 2. The Average tensile strength of host composite laminate which was used as a reference stress for the fatigue life test of sensors.

Optical fiber	Stacking sequence	Stiffness (GPa)	Strength (MPa)
With 1 O. F.	Crossply	19.94	339.80
	Unidirectional	38.42	993.44
Without O. F.	Crossply	19.44	332.58
	Unidirectional	36.88	954.46

experiments are in progress.

Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 show the S-N curves for the optical fiber embedded in the unidirectional specimens and crossply specimens respectively. The fatigue limits of two S-N curves are around 15% of strength of each host composite laminte. The S-N curves is composed of two region. One is low cycle fatigue region above the stress level of about 15%, and the other is infinite life region under the fatigue limit of the stress level of about 15%. In the low cycle fatigue region, the logarithm of fatigue life of optical fiber decreases linearly as the maximum stress level increases. From these figures, it is found that the embedded optical fiber sensor has very low resistance to the fatigue load compared to host structure.

Figure 7. S-N curve for the optical fiber embedded in the unidirectional specimen.

Figure 8. S-N curve for optical fiber embedded in the crossply specimen.

This means that smart structures should be designed to be subjected to lower cyclic stress than the fatigue limit of embedded optical fiber to ensure the integrity of the embedded optical fiber sensors in addition to host structure itself.

CONCLUSION

In this study, the fatigue characteristics of composite laminates with embedded optical fibers were evaluated in order to investigate the effect of embedded optical fiber sensors on the mechanical behavior of composite laminates under the fatigue load. The fatigue life of embedded optical fiber was also evaluated to investigate the integrity of embedded optical fiber sensors itself in the smart structure working under cyclic load. The following results were obtained:

Under the fatigue loading, it was observed that the embedded optical fiber sensors may cause significant effect on the fatigue life of smart composite structures and these embedded optical fiber sensors show very low resistance to the fatigue loads. The observed fatigue limit of these sensors were around 15% of strength of host composite structures. However, the embedded optical fiber sensors did not show significant effect on the matrix cracking behavior of crossply specimens under the fatigue loading. From these results, it can be said that for the whole integrity of smart structures, the optimal design stresses may be reduced due to the embedding of optical fiber sensors.

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